

Reforms of Goods Services Taxes

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Abstract

The GST was launched at midnight on 1 July 2017 by the President of India, Pranab Mukherjee, and the Government of India. The launch was marked by a historic midnight (30 June – 1 July) session of both the houses of parliament convened at the Central Hall of the Parliament. Goods and services are divided into five tax slabs for collection of tax - 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. However, Petroleum products, alcoholic drinks, electricity, and real estate are not taxed under GST and instead are taxed separately by the individual state governments, as per the previous tax regime. There is a special rate of 0.25% on rough precious and semi-precious stones and 3% on gold.[1] In addition a cess of 22% or other rates on top of 28% GST applies on few items like aerated drinks, luxury cars and tobacco products. Pre-GST, the statutory tax rate for most goods was about 26.5%, Post-GST, most goods are expected to be in the 18% tax range. The single GST subsumed several taxes and levies which included: central excise duty, services tax, additional customs duty, surcharges, state-level value added tax and Octroi. Other levies which were applicable on inter-state transportation of goods have also been done away with in GST regime. GST is levied on all transactions such as sale, transfer, purchase, barter, lease, or import of goods and/or services. The GST is imposed at variable rates on variable items. The rate of GST is 18% for soaps and 28% on washing detergents. GST on movie tickets is based on slabs, with 18% GST for tickets that cost less than Rs. 100 and 28% GST on tickets costing more than Rs.100 and 5% on readymade clothes. The rate on under-construction property booking is 12% Some industries and products were exempted by the government and remain untaxed under GST, such as dairy products, products of milling industries, fresh vegetables & fruits, meat products, and other groceries and necessities.

Keywords: GST – Introduction – Objective - Review of Literature - Reforms of GST - Impact of GST – Revenue of GST

Introduction

The GST was launched at midnight on 1 July 2017 by the President of India, Pranab Mukherjee, and the Government of India. The launch was marked by a historic midnight (30 June – 1 July) session of both the houses of parliament convened at the Central Hall of the Parliament. Goods and services are divided into five tax slabs for collection of tax - 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28%. The GSTN software is developed by Infosys Technologies and the Information Technology network that provides the computing resources is maintained by the NIC. “Goods and Services Tax” Network (GSTN) is a nonprofit organisation formed for creating a sophisticated network, accessible to stakeholders, government and taxpayers to access information from a single source (portal). The portal is accessible to the Tax authorities for tracking down every transaction, while taxpayers have the ability of connect for their tax returns.

Objectives of the Study

- The single GST subsumed several taxes and levies which included: central excise duty, services tax, additional customs duty, surcharges, state-level value added tax and Octroi.
- Other levies which were applicable on inter-state transportation of goods have also been done away with in GST regime. GST is levied on all transactions such as sale, transfer, purchase, barter, lease, or import of goods and/or services.
- India adopted a dual GST model, meaning that taxation is administered by both the Union and State Governments. Transactions made within a single state are levied with Central GST (CGST) by the Central Government and State GST (SGST) by the State governments. For inter-state transactions and imported goods or services, an Integrated GST (IGST) is levied by the Central Government.
- GST is a consumption-based tax/destination-based tax, therefore, taxes are paid to the state where the goods or services are consumed not the state in which they were produced. IGST complicates tax collection for State Governments by disabling them from collecting the tax owed to them directly from the Central Government. Under the previous system, a state would only have to deal with a single government in order to collect tax revenue.

Literature Review

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Reforms of GST

- **On growth** the GST is, other things being equal, decisively positive for long-term sustainable economic growth compared to the massively confusing “VAT + excise + service tax + octroi + other taxes and duties” regime that existed earlier. This indeed represents India signing a revolutionary “free trade deal with itself”.
- **The order effect of growth is of course higher** tax revenue – one through existing tax payers paying more, and second through the impact of formalisation (unorganised firms are finding it much more difficult to remain a part of larger supply chains without coming into the GST system). Indeed, around 11 million businesses are registered under GST out of which almost 5 million are new registrations!
- **There is a tertiary impact of indirect tax** returns being matched against direct returns through analytics, and consequent higher compliance there as well. Indeed, we have seen a bump in tax revenue though it is too soon to disentangle the various possible sources – GST, demonetisation, bottoming out of the business cycle, digitalization, other reforms etc. To conclude, the GST is good for growth, formalisation and state capacity although any one number about percentage increase in long-term growth should be taken with a pinch of salt. However, the GST has been criticised on grounds of efficiency itself because of the multiple tax rates – that point is addressed below.

- **On the equity** it is true that having fewer tax rates – or one tax rate to take the purist view – would be considered good for growth in the neoclassical economics’ view. Moreover, having less tweaking with rates by having fewer rates certainly reduces the chances of cronyism or political favouritism. But this should be weighed against two concerns: equity (or “progressivity”), Accepts the normative view that the rich must not only pay more taxes but that they should pay a higher share of their income in taxes as well for the system to be morally legitimate. Further, even if there were no equity concerns, a case can be made that incentivising savings and discouraging luxury or “conspicuous” or “sinful” consumption through tax rate tweaks (not crude bans etc.) may help economic growth (through more investments) or social stability or both (though, one must always be sceptical - but not cynical - when it comes to such social engineering).
- **On the federalism** the GST as it stands today has been a brilliant example of cooperative federalism and political leadership but it is still a potentially worrying development when it comes to competitive federalism – because states once they think beyond guaranteed revenues will realise that they still control spending but not tax generation policies, except collectively with other states and the centre. This is likely to lead to higher-than-otherwise but nonetheless lower quality expenditure at the state level, and the central government is likely to face the consequences of these misaligned incentives at some point. The good news is that whatever needs to be changed has been provided by the system itself – namely, the critical GST IT network (GSTN) which lets the government verify that what X Co. in Punjab said it bought from Y Co. in Kerala (or indeed in Punjab itself) was actually bought and at that price.
- **Member** Dr. Hasmukh Adhia, IAS introduction the plaque to inaugurate the New GST Council Office, GST council is the governing body of GST having 33 members. It is chaired by the Union Finance Minister.

Revenue of GST

Data: Press Information Bureau

Impact of GST on The Indian Economy

GST the biggest tax reform in India founded on the notion of “one nation, one market, one tax” is finally here. The moment that the Indian government was waiting for a decade has finally arrived. The single biggest indirect tax regime has kicked into force, dismantling all the inter-state barriers with respect to trade. The GST rollout, with a single stroke, has converted India into a unified

market of 1.3 billion citizens. Fundamentally, the \$2.4-trillion economy is attempting to transform itself by doing away with the internal tariff barriers and subsuming central, state and local taxes into a unified GST.

Impact of GST on Manufacturers, Distributor, and Retailers

GST is a boost competitiveness and performance in India's manufacturing sector. Declining exports and high infrastructure spending are just some of the concerns of this sector. Multiple indirect taxes had also increased the administrative costs for manufacturers and distributors and with GST in place, the compliance burden has eased and this sector will grow more strongly. But due to GST business which was not under the tax bracket previously will now have to register. This will lead to lesser tax evasion.

Impact of GST on Service Providers: As of March 2014, there were 12, 76,861 service tax assesseees in the country out of which only the top 50 paid more than 50% of the tax collected nationwide. Most of the tax burden is borne by domains such as IT services, telecommunication services, the Insurance industry, business support services, Banking and Financial services, etc. These pan-India businesses already work in a unified market and will see compliance burden becoming lesser. But they will have to separately register every place of business in each state.

Sector-wise Impact Analysis

Logistics: In a vast country like India, the logistics sector forms the backbone of the economy. We can fairly assume that a well organized and mature logistics industry has the potential to leapfrog the "Make In India" initiative of the Government of India to its desired position.

E-commerce: The e-commerce sector in India has been growing by leaps and bounds. In many ways, GST will help the e-com sector's continued growth but the long-term effects will be particularly interesting because the GST law specifically proposes a Tax Collection at Source (TCS) mechanism, which e-com companies are not too happy with. The current rate of TCS is at 1%.

Pharma: On the whole, GST is benefiting the pharma and healthcare industries. It will create a level playing field for generic drug makers, boost medical tourism and simplify the tax structure. If there is any concern whatsoever, then it relates to the pricing structure (as per latest news). The pharma sector is hoping for a tax respite as it will make affordable healthcare easier to access by all.

Telecommunications : In the telecom sector, prices will come down after GST. Manufacturers will save on costs through efficient management of inventory and by consolidating their warehouses. Handset manufacturers will find it easier to sell their equipment as GST has negated the need to set up state-specific entities, and transfer stocks. They will also save up on logistics costs.

Textile: The Indian textile industry provides employment to a large number of skilled and unskilled workers in the country. It contributes about 10% of the total annual export, and this value is likely to increase under GST. GST would affect the cotton value chain of the textile industry which is chosen by most small medium enterprises as it previously attracted zero central excise duty (under optional route).

Real Estate: The real estate sector is one of the most pivotal sectors of the Indian economy, playing an important role in employment generation in India. The impact of GST on the real estate sector cannot be fully assessed as it largely depends on the tax rates. However, the sector will see substantial benefits from GST implementation, as it has brought to the industry much-required transparency and accountability.

Agriculture: The agricultural sector is the largest contributing sector the overall Indian GDP. It covers around 16% of Indian GDP. One of the major issues faced by the agricultural sector is the transportation of agri-products across state lines all over India. GST will resolve the issue of transportation.

FMCG: The FMCG sector is experiencing significant savings in logistics and distribution costs as the GST has eliminated the need for multiple sales depots.

Freelancers: Freelancing in India is still a nascent industry and the rules and regulations for this chaotic industry are still up in the air. But with GST, it will become much easier for freelancers to file their taxes as they can easily do it online. They are taxed as service providers, and the new tax structure has brought about coherence and accountability in this sector.

Automobiles: The automobile industry in India is a vast business producing a large number of cars annually, fueled mostly by the huge population of the country. Under the previous tax system, there were several taxes applicable to this sector like excise, VAT, sales tax, road tax, motor vehicle tax, registration duty which will be subsumed by GST.

GST: The Short-Term Impact: From the viewpoint of the consumer, they would now have pay more tax for most of the goods and services they consume. The majority of everyday consumables now draw the same or a slightly higher rate of tax. Furthermore, the GST implementation has a cost of compliance attached to it. It seems that this cost of compliance will be prohibitive and high for the small scale manufacturers and traders, who have also protested against the same. They may end up pricing their goods at higher rates.

What the Future Looks Like: Talking about the long-term benefits, it is expected that GST would not just mean a lower rate of taxes, but also minimum tax slabs. Countries where the Goods and Service Tax has helped in reforming the economy, apply only 2 or 3 rates – one being the mean rate, a lower rate for essential commodities, and a higher tax rate for the luxurious commodities. Currently, in India, we have 5 slabs, with as many as 3 rates – an integrated rate, a central rate, and a state rate. In addition to these, cess is also levied. The fear of losing out on revenue has kept the government from gambling on fewer or lower rates. This is very unlikely to see a shift anytime soon; though the government has said that rates may be revisited once the RNR (revenue neutral rate) is reached.

The impact of GST on macroeconomic indicators: It is likely to be very positive in the medium-term. Inflation would be reduced as the cascading (tax on tax) effect of taxes would be eliminated. The revenue from the taxes for the government is very likely to increase with an extended tax net, and the fiscal deficit is expected to remain under the checks. Moreover, exports would grow, while FDI (Foreign Direct Investment) would also increase. The industry leaders believe that the country would climb several ladders in the ease of doing business with the implementation of the most important tax reform ever in the history of the country.

Conclusion

On priority, it is up to the government to address the capacity building amongst the lesser-endowed participants, such as the small-scale manufacturers and traders. Ways have to be found for lowering the overall compliance cost, and necessary changes may have to be made for the good of the masses. GST will become good and simple, only when the entire country works as a whole towards making it successful.

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